

Offshore Wind Farm Planning and Socioecological Trade-Offs: Wake-Induced Primary Productivity Disruptions

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Research group

This research project was conducted within the LIVENlab research line, which is part of the Sostenipra Research Group at the Institute of Environmental Science and Technology, Autonomous University of Barcelona (ICTA-UAB). The primary objective of the LIVENlab is to develop an environmental assessment tool that enhances decision-making in selecting energy policies within specific geographical locations.

More specifically, this study aligns with the ongoing efforts of the JUSTWIND4ALL project, where our contribution lies in conducting a comprehensive assessment of the impacts of wind energy. We achieve this by identifying potential impactors using Parc Tramuntana (PT), Spain's first pilot offshore wind farm in the northwest Mediterranean Sea (NWM), as a case study.

The current study fits within the scope of the LIVENlab by aiming to develop knowledge and tools that facilitate informed decision-making in wind energy policies, with a specific focus on promoting the sustainability of energy systems, particularly within the Catalan electricity production system. This contribution is realized through the assessment of environmental impacts associated with electricity production under different scenarios, adopting a life cycle perspective. Overall, this study also contributes to the advancement of environmental assessments for renewable energy planning, ultimately optimizing the sustainability of energy decarbonization strategies.

Contribution

The current study emanates from the student's own work under the supervision of Dr. Cristina Madrid López. The project is characterized by an initial identification of a research gap and exploring a case study using a literature review and life cycle analysis (LCA). The findings were compiled into this document representing the student's work and highlighting the valuable insights gained from the research process.

Journal Guidelines

Journal: Global Environmental Change

- Research articles present original research and are up to 8,000 words in length, including main body text, table and figure captions but not including references. All manuscripts must contain the essential elements needed to convey your manuscript - Abstract, Keywords, Introduction, Methods, Results, Conclusions, Figures and Tables with Captions. Divide your article into clearly defined and numbered sections. Subsections should be numbered 1.1 (then 1.1.1, 1.1.2, ...), 1.2, etc. (the abstract is not included in section numbering).
- Introduction: State the objectives of the work and provide an adequate background, avoiding a detailed literature survey or a summary of the results.
- Material and methods: Provide sufficient details to allow the work to be reproduced by an independent researcher. Methods that are already published should be summarized, and indicated by a reference. If quoting directly from a previously published method, use quotation marks and also cite the source. Any modifications to existing methods should also be described.
- Theory/calculation: A Theory section should extend, not repeat, the background to the article already dealt with in the Introduction and lay the foundation for further work. In contrast, a Calculation section represents a practical development from a theoretical basis.

- Results: Results should be clear and concise.
- Discussion: This should explore the significance of the results of the work, not repeat them. A combined Results and Discussion section is often appropriate. Avoid extensive citations and discussion of published literature.
- Conclusions: The main conclusions of the study may be presented in a short Conclusions section, which may stand alone or form a subsection of a Discussion or Results and Discussion section.
- Appendices: If there is more than one appendix, they should be identified as A, B, etc. Formulae and equations in appendices should be given separate numbering: Eq. (A.1), Eq. (A.2), etc.; in a subsequent appendix, Eq. (B.1) and so on. Similarly for tables and figures: Table A.1; Fig. A.1, etc.
- Abstract: A concise and factual abstract is required. The abstract should state briefly the purpose of the research, the principal results and major conclusions. An abstract is often presented separately from the article, so it must be able to stand alone. For this reason, references should be avoided, but if essential, then cite the author(s) and year(s).
- Keywords: Immediately after the abstract, provide a maximum of 6 keywords, using American spelling and avoiding general and plural terms and multiple concepts (avoid, for example, 'and', 'of'). Be sparing with abbreviations: only abbreviations firmly established in the field may be eligible.
- Electronic artwork: Make sure you use uniform lettering and sizing of your original artwork. Preferred fonts: Arial (or Helvetica), Times New Roman (or Times), Symbol, Courier. Number the illustrations according to their sequence in the text. Use a logical naming convention for your artwork files.
- Figure captions: Ensure that each illustration has a caption. A caption should comprise a brief title (not on the figure itself) and a description of the illustration. Keep text in the illustrations themselves to a minimum but explain all symbols and abbreviations used.
- Tables: Please submit tables as editable text and not as images. Tables can be placed either next to the relevant text in the article, or on separate page(s) at the end. Number tables consecutively in accordance with their appearance in the text and place any table notes below the table body. Be sparing in the use of tables and ensure that the data presented in them do not duplicate results described elsewhere in the article. Please avoid using vertical rules and shading in table cells.

Offshore Wind Farm Planning and Socioecological Trade-Offs: Wake-Induced Primary Productivity Disruptions

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Abstract

The growing demand for renewable energy and the imperative to decarbonize energy systems have spurred the rapid development of offshore wind farms (OWFs) in coastal regions. However, our grasp of the ecological and social consequences of these installations remains incomplete. This research delves into the socioecological tradeoffs linked to OWF implementation, specifically examining the potential effects of the wake effect on primary productivity (PP) and carbon sequestration in marine ecosystems. Parc Tramuntana (PT) in the Northwest Mediterranean (NWM), known for its robust wind-induced stratified mixing and rich biodiversity, serves as the case study. The wake effect stemming from OWFs can have varying impacts on PP, depending on temporal and spatial scales. PT can substitute 4.2% of Catalonia's current energy mix for offshore wind energy, leading to a 14% reduction in global warming potential (GWP). Still, further investigation is required to elucidate the potential tradeoff with PP loss or eutrophication. Our comprehension of socioecological tradeoffs in OWFs is hindered by knowledge gaps in ecosystem responses. Life cycle assessment (LCA) models, which primarily focus on overall impacts, fail to capture this phenomenon, underscoring the necessity for site-specific studies and comprehensive assessment tools like Multi-scale Integrated Analysis of Societal and Ecosystem Metabolism (MuSIASEM). Such tools enable analysis of energy, material, and information flows in socio-ecological systems, to better inform policy decisions surrounding renewable electricity systems.

Graphical Abstract

Keywords: offshore wind farms (OWF), primary productivity (PP), wake effect, energy modelling

1. Introduction

1.1 Research Context

Decades of fossil fuel-powered economic activity and corresponding greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions have had multiscale destabilizing effects on ecosystem dynamics and the supporting role they play in life on earth (IPCC, 2013). With ecosystems teetering on the brink of tipping points, the pressure for institutional change is mounting and international initiatives are starting to catalyze the decarbonization of energy systems (Black et al., 2021). As nations strive to achieve carbon-neutral targets, wind energy emerges as a pivotal element in their endeavors, prompting a focus on coastal regions as promising frontiers for renewable energy production. In the European Union (EU), member states are mandated to fulfill 40% of their energy requirements through wind power by 2030, with offshore wind farms (OWFs) projected to account for 76% of anticipated installations in Europe by 2026 (WindEurope, 2022).

However, marine ecosystems provide a number of vital services to the biosphere, including the crucial roles of nutrient cycling and primary production that support aquatic food webs and regulate global CO₂ levels. Yet, offshore wind is still an emerging industry, and the social and environmental impacts of OWFs on surrounding ecosystems are largely unknown. While the value of these services is currently not accounted for in energy modelling, a holistic incorporation of ecosystem dynamics into such metrics will help clarify trade-off decisions and support informed policy making. The rapid upscaling of offshore wind energy calls for the development of comprehensive metrics and modelling tools to effectively understand and mitigate the potential social and ecological consequences of OWF operation.

1.2 Biogeochemical Dynamics

The wake effect is one such potential impactor commonly observed in wind farms. The effect occurs as wind turbines rotate and generate electricity, extracting kinetic energy from the atmosphere. The result is decreased wind speeds and increased turbulence in the wake of OWFs (Christiansen et al., 2013; Ahktar et al., 2021; Van Berkel et al., 2020). This study will focus on how this effect impacts other biogeochemical dynamics in marine ecosystems as illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Two convergent pathways for the flow of kinetic wind energy: (A) into the offshore wind system in which renewable electricity is generated, or (B) into the marine ecosystem in which mixing of the stratified water column leads to a upwelling of nutrients like nitrogen and phosphorous (N,P). This nutrient enrichment supports photosynthesis in the euphotic layer, where microscopic phytoplankton serve as the primary food source for the entire trophic system and facilitate the conversion of CO₂ into organic carbon. Carbon sequestration is facilitated through the export of dissolved and particulate organic carbon (DOC/POC) to the sea floor.

In aquatic ecosystems, wind mixes vertical layers of the water column that have been separated by a temperature gradient called the thermocline. The thermocline acts as a barrier between layers, trapping phytoplankton (primary producers) in the warm, upper, sunlit layer (the euphotic layer) while trapping nutrients like nitrogen and phosphorous in the cold, deeper layers of the water column. The availability of nitrogen tends to be a limiting factor of photosynthesis in marine ecosystems (Ryther and Dunstan 1971; Vitousek et al. 2002; Howarth and Marino 2006; Hood and Christian 2008). Therefore, the wind acts as a key agent in marine photosynthesis by mixing surface waters which leads to an upwelling of nutrients to the euphotic layer.

Among its many contributions, photosynthesis supports two major ecosystem services: primary production (PP) and carbon sequestration. Phytoplankton serve as the base of trophic chains by converting sunlight, water, CO₂, and nutrients into food, thus acting as the primary food source for nearly all marine organisms. Concurrently, CO₂ is taken out of atmospheric circulation through its conversion to organic carbon where it can be exported to and stored in the sea floor for extended periods of time, thus, mitigating climate change.

1.3 Case Study Definition

Ecosystem Characteristics

PT will be constructed in the NWM, a seasonally stratified sea shelf where wind stress serves as a key agent in trophic dynamics (Dorrell et al., 2022; Van Berkel et al., 2020). The NWM has been found to host the most intense and recurrent episodes of wind-induced vertical mixing and corresponding spikes in PP within the Mediterranean (D’Ortenzio & Ribera d’Alcalà, 2009; Houpert et al., 2015; Lavigne, 2013; Mayot et al., 2016). These dynamics are responsible for the unusually high biodiversity observed in this region compared to the largely oligotrophic

Mediterranean (Alcaraz et al., 2007). As such, the local biogeochemical dynamics could be sensitive to wind wakes with considerable implications for cascading trophic levels and local biodiversity (Lloret et al., 2022). Additionally, high PP in this region resulting from these processes has also been known to promote particulate carbon export to the sea floor (Gogou et al., 2014; Ulses et al., 2016). This implies the region plays a significant role in carbon capture in the Mediterranean. Estimates dictate that the Mediterranean Sea acts as a carbon sink, sequestering 17.8 million tons CO₂/yr with the Spanish exclusive economic zone (EEZ) as a top contributor (Melaku Canu et al., 2015).

Electricity Production in Catalonia

Only 20% of Catalonia's electricity grid is currently supplied by renewable energy, with nuclear power as the primary source of electricity production (Institut Català d'Energia, 2022). The nuclear reactors, Ascó I & II and Vandellós II recently received extended authorization to operate until 2030 (Ministerio para la Transición Ecológica y el Reto Demográfico, 2020). Meanwhile, renewable energy objectives require Catalonia to incorporate 1,000 MW of offshore wind power into the electricity grid by 2030 (Institut Català d'Energia, 2023). Catalonia's 2050 Energy Outlook (Prospectiva Energètica de Catalunya, PROENCAT 2050) proposes that with the incorporation of offshore wind and other forms of renewable energy, the autonomous community can achieve 50% renewable electricity production by 2030 and 100% by 2050 (Institut Català d'Energia, 2023).

In response to the approaching expirations of Ascó I&II and Vandellós II and the arrival of renewable energy targets, the installation of PT is planned to begin in 2025. The park will consist of 33 floating 15 MW turbines projected to supply 45% of the annual electricity demands of Girona, or ~4.22% total electricity demand in Catalonia, and prevent 16 million tons of CO₂ emissions with an expected operation timeline from 2026 to 2051 (Parc Tramuntana, 2023).

1.4 Objectives

The objective of this study is to assess the tradeoffs of offshore wind farms by comparing the projected carbon emissions saved by renewable energy implementation in Catalonia to the potential carbon sequestration lost through wake-induced changes in PP.

2. Methodology

2.1 Literature Review

A structured literature review was conducted to explore the socioecological tradeoffs of OWF implementation in Catalonia. The primary question posed was: 'How does the wake effect produced by offshore wind farms affect socioecological systems in Catalonia?' This question was divided into secondary questions encompassing more concise topics including: What are the impacts of the wake effect on PP? What are the socioecological interaction pathways downstream of the wake effect in the NWM?

Standard literature databases like Google Scholar, Web of Science, and Scopus were searched for the literature collection using the strategies of keyword searches and citation chaining to identify relevant scientific information about the socioecological impacts of wake-induced changes

in PP, filtering for publications between 2013 to 2023. Key words included: offshore wind (OWF), primary productivity, nutrient mixing, the wake effect, northwest Mediterranean (NWM).

2.2 Assessing Emissions and Other Impacts

We conducted a Life Cycle Analysis (LCA) to compare the environmental impacts of four different plausible electricity production scenarios in Catalonia per megawatt hour (MWh) of electricity generated. LCA is a method that measures the environmental impacts of a product or process over its entire life cycle. The four scenarios considered were the current baseline electricity production mix in Catalonia, a PT scenario which substitutes Combined Heat and Power (CHP) for offshore wind, the PROENCAT 2030 proposed mix, and the PROENCAT 2050 proposed mix. The components of each energy system are outlined in Table 1. Because the nuclear reactors are expected to operate until 2030, it is assumed that the electricity generated by PT will serve to replace CHP. The rest of the inputs are based on Catalonia electricity production statistics for the year 2022 (Institut Català d'Energia, 2022). The 2030 and 2050 inputs are based on projections from the PROENCAT 2050 Report (Institut Català d'Energia, 2023).

Baseline Mix		Parc Tramuntana Mix		PROENCAT Scenario 2030		PROENCAT Scenario 2050	
Production Type	Contribution	Production Type	Contribution	Production Type	Contribution	Production Type	Contribution
Nuclear	56.2%	Nuclear	56.2%	Nuclear	50.0%	Onshore Wind	39.8%
CHP	26.9%	CHP	22.7%	Onshore Wind	19.9%	Photovoltaic Ground	27.8%
Hydroelectricity	6.8%	Hydroelectric	6.8%	Photovoltaic Ground	11.1%	Photovoltaic Roof and Other	16.4%
Onshore Wind	5.8%	Onshore Wind	5.8%	Hydroelectricity	6.3%	Offshore Wind	11.4%
Roof Photovoltaic	2.0%	Offshore Wind	4.2%	Offshore Wind	5.9%	Hydroelectricity	3.6%
		Roof Photovoltaic	2.0%	Photovoltaic Roof and Other	5.5%		

Table 1. Types and amounts of each energy input for four different electricity production scenarios in Catalonia.

The tradeoffs between the benefits of offshore wind-generated electricity and the effects of wake-induced PP fluctuations were explored through the comparison of the global warming potentials (GWP) and marine eutrophication potentials (MEP) of the first two scenarios. The PROENCAT scenarios were included in this study to explore these tradeoffs as offshore wind development in Catalonia is upscaled. The 2050 scenario represents Catalonia's full offshore wind capacity by including all technically viable OWF sites along the Catalan coast in its projection.

Each scenario was simulated using the *OpenLCA* software and the *Eco-invent v3.5* database which contains inventories designed to represent global and local supply chains and product flows as accurately as possible within the scope of this project. The method *ReCiPe 2008* was implemented to assess the impacts of each scenario over a 100-year time horizon with a hierarchist perspective selected to strike the middle ground between short-term and long-term impacts. The final impact calculation of each scenario incorporates the aggregated upstream impacts of each energy input from material extraction to use and maintenance (Annex I). This was a cursory model that did not divulge sensitivity data.

3. Results

3.1 Socioecological Interactions Downwind of the Wake Effect in Parc Tramuntana

Ecological Impacts

The wake effect has been projected to result in decreases in annual wind speed anywhere from to 10-20% (Akhtar et al., 2021; Christensen et al., 2013) across an area up to 100 times the size of the OWF itself in extreme cases (Ludewig, 2015). Studies estimate that these changes to the wind field will result in not only reductions PP, but also increases in annual PP by as much as $\pm 10\%$ (Daewel et al., 2022).

Wake-induced increases in PP are a result of increased turbulence, a known driver of vertical mixing under certain circumstances (Broström, 2008; Krause et al., 1986; Fennel et al., 1991). Meanwhile, other studies indicate offshore wind submerged infrastructure might increase nutrient mixing by adding turbulence to the water column at the thermocline (Dorrell et al., 2022; Floeter et al., 2017). Empirical evidence suggests a positive or negative PP response depends on temporal and spatial scales. While increases of nutrient mixing over shorter time periods results in pulses of increased PP, an overall decrease in mixing and corresponding reduction of PP over a longer (monthly) scale was observed due to the spatial nature of the wakes created (Floeter et al., 2017) (Floeter et al., 2022).

Social Impacts

From an economic standpoint, interruptions to trophic dynamics can have social ripples via the local fishing economy. The Gulf of Roses alone is responsible for providing 911.1 tons of catch translating to €14.27 million of income in 2022 (Gencat, 2023). Furthermore, while the human welfare benefits of carbon sequestration are difficult to quantify, a study by Melaku Canu et al. estimated that the carbon sequestration services of the Mediterranean region of Spain's EEZ have been valued to equvalate 114.0 €/km²/year in abatement and damage costs of global impacts (2015).

3.2 Life Cycle Impact Analysis

Global Warming Potential

The PT, PROENCAT 2030, and PROENCAT 2050 scenarios were all estimated to reduce the GWP from the current electricity production mix in Catalonia by 14%, 85%, and 75%, respectively (Figure 3). However, the turbines to be installed in PT will have a capacity of 15 MW and floating foundation technology. Evidence suggests this will result in an overshoot of the predicted GWP/MWh of offshore wind electricity generation in this analysis (Caduff et al., 2012). The main contributor to GWP proved to be the fossil-related CO₂ emissions produced by the CHP which makes up 80% of the climate change contribution of the current mix (Figure 4). The elimination of CHP from the mixes in the PROENCAT scenarios resulted in significantly reduced contributions to global warming (Figure 4). The non-intuitive increase in GWP from the 2030 scenario to the 2050 scenario was due to the upscaling of ground photovoltaic electricity production (Figure 4).

Marine Eutrophication Potential

All three offshore wind energy scenarios show a reduction in MEP from the current energy mix in Catalonia (Figure 3). CHP and nuclear power contributed the most to MEP in the current mix and PT scenarios through the release of nitrate and nitrogen oxides (Figure 5). This indicator captures the impacts caused by nitrogen-based emissions to the ground, air, and water and does not account for potential wake-induced eutrophication.

Figure 2. Life cycle impact analyses for each electricity production scenario.

Figure 3. Contribution analysis for GWP for each electricity production scenario. CHP – combined heat and power, N – nuclear, RP – rooftop photovoltaic, GP – ground photovoltaic, ON – onshore wind, OF – offshore wind, H – hydroelectricity.

Figure 4. Contribution analysis for GWP for each electricity production scenario. CHP – combined heat and power, N – nuclear, RP – rooftop photovoltaic, GP – ground photovoltaic, ON – onshore wind, OF – offshore wind, H – hydroelectricity.

4. Discussion

The substitution of CHP, accounting for 4.22% of the energy mix, for offshore wind energy in the current electricity scenario in Catalonia resulted in a projected 14% reduction of GWP; reductions in GWP by 85% and 74% were predicted when CHP was completely eliminated in the 2030 and 2050 scenarios. The counterintuitive increase in GWP in the 100% renewable energy 2050 scenario reveals that photovoltaic inputs proved to be the largest GWP contributors amongst the assessed renewable energies.

While studies suggest the wake-induced PP fluctuations up to 10% are potential outcomes of OWF, the correlation between these changes and the rate of carbon sequestration requires a more nuanced assessment. The potential of the wake effect to disrupt PP to a degree in which it would counteract the carbon savings generated from offshore wind energy deployment is unknown.

Furthermore, while the current literature mainly describes potential responses of PP to the wake effect in the North Sea, studies specific to the NWM ecosystem are lacking. The NWM hydrogeological features and unique position as hub of biodiversity compared to the rest of the Mediterranean problematizes the reliance on North Sea studies for predicting outcomes. Site-specific research in this region is needed to adequately predict the responses of the socioecological system that surrounds PT. Considering the major role played by the Spanish EEZ in Mediterranean carbon capture, it is important that this effect is adequately monitored and understood.

A major limitation was the unavailability of accurate inventory data. The incorporation of lower capacity turbines in this analysis likely overstates the GWP contributions of the PT electricity production scenario (Caduff et al., 2012). It is also worth noting that increased vertical mixing due to submerged infrastructure will likely be less of an impact factor in PT due to the semi-submersible floating technology which significantly reduces interactions with the water column.

The literature review revealed that in certain circumstances, the wake effect results in a netPP gain due to increased vertical mixing caused by turbulence. In this case, the outcome could be either positive or negative. Excessive PP can lead to eutrophication which poses significant ecological risks and threatens the health and biodiversity of aquatic ecosystems. In the case of PT, the LCIA predicted a 6.8% decrease in marine eutrophication from the current electricity mix in Catalonia with only 1.27% of this impact is derived from offshore wind in the PT scenario, indicating a compatibility between OWFs and the marine environment in this respect. It is worth noting that marine eutrophication induced by the wake effect is not currently accounted for in LCA models.

Conversely, moderate increases in PP can help support the provisioning and carbon sequestration services provided to ecosystems by phytoplankton. The potential for OWFs to have positive environmental outcomes has opened an ongoing discourse around coordinating OWF planning with OECMs (other effective area-based conservation measures) and other nature-based solutions (NbS). The *de facto* protection from harmful fishing methods like bottom trawling in OWFs is often highlighted as one of these benefits. Being surrounded by eight MPAs (marine protected areas) that safeguard habitats important to this region, PT may have the potential to act

as an additional protective buffer (Lloret et al., 2022). Another potential NbS in OWF planning that is currently being explored is the co-location of OWF with seagrass farms, which could generate substantial ecosystem benefits including food web connectivity, biodiversity support, and carbon offsetting. The 2023 initiation of a seagrass farm/OFW in the Dutch North Sea marks the first attempt at this type of coordinated marine spatial planning effort (Lewis, 2023).

Conclusion

In conclusion, the predicted tradeoffs of the wake effect in PT are highly uncertain at this point. Although the wake effect is a phenomenon that is likely to have environmental impacts on GWP and MEP, it is not captured by LCA models which primarily focus on the life cycle impacts of a product or process. This calls for the site-specific study of the wake effect and the continued expansion and development of comprehensive assessment tools like MuSIASEM (Multi-scale Integrated Analysis of Societal and Ecosystem Metabolism), which takes a broader perspective by analyzing the interactions and flows of energy, materials, and information within socio-ecological systems and is better suited to capture the complexity of energy flows through a renewable electricity system.

Beyond that, knowledge gaps about ecosystem responses to the wake effect inhibit the holistic comprehension of socioecological tradeoffs in OWFs. Yet, as the incorporation of new innovations and nature-based solutions into marine spatial planning expands, the potential negative effects of such interventions merit careful consideration. Redesigning energy systems to mitigate the globally pressing issue of climate change is a crucial yet complex endeavor. In the pursuit of developing solutions to this issue, we must acknowledge that alongside their potential benefits, they also give rise to significant local impacts.

Annex I

LCA Methodological Set Up

Figure 5. Life cycle impact analysis of energy systems incorporates the impacts of processes upstream of the system including material extraction and processing, energy production, transportation, manufacturing, use, and maintenance.

LCA Assumptions

- (1) Although the CHP sources are not detailed in Catalonia's energy statistics website, Naturgy, the utility owner of most CHP plants is a natural gas company. Therefore, we assumed that the fuel source of CHHP in Catalonia is natural gas.
- (2) 3kWp, slanted-roof, installation, multi-Si, mounted panels used for roof photovoltaic production.
- (3) 570kWp open ground installation, multi-Si, used for ground photovoltaic production.
- (4) Because the nuclear reactors were granted a 10 extension of operation until 2030, it is assumed that the electricity generated by PT will serve to replace CHP from the current mix.
- (5) In the PROENCAT 2050 report, the Catalan Energy Institute projects that by the year 2030 electricity in Catalonia can be 50% generated by renewable energy. Because the nuclear reactors

were granted a 10 extension of operation until 2030, we assumed the 50% non-renewable input in the 2030 PROENCAT scenario will come from nuclear power.

Normalization

In each scenario, 1-3% of the electricity production came from unlisted sources. The deal with these gaps, the portions of the mix that were sourced by 'other' energy inputs were excluded from the calculation and the total electricity production was normalized to the sum of known energy inputs.

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Nikki Harasta: Conceptualization, Analysis, Writing - Original Draft, Visualization **Cristina Madrid López, PhD:** Conceptualization, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition

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